

Kinetics and reaction mechanism of the controlled oxidation of some industrial alcohols by haloamines

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Abstract : A kinetic study of the controlled oxidation of perfumery alcohols, geraniol, 1-phenyl ethanol and benzyl alcohol by Chloramine T in alkaline medium and Chloramine B in acidic medium has been carried out in the temperature range 30 °C to 50 °C. The oxidation was monitored in the micellar phase using sodium dodecyl sulphate.

The oxidation rate increases with alcohol concentration but decreases with the concentration of the oxidising reagent and varies linearly with the concentration of the metal ion catalysts used. The thermodynamic activation parameters have been calculated.

Keywords : Perfumery alcohols, micellar phase, oxidation.

Oxidation of alcohols is a reaction of prime industrial importance. Much work has been reported on the quantitative conversion of alcohols to carbonyl compounds¹. But there are comparatively few reports of the kinetic and thermodynamic aspects of oxidation of alcohols². In this paper, the kinetics of the oxidation of the perfumery alcohols, geraniol, 1-phenyl ethanol and benzyl alcohol by Chloramine T in NaOH and Chloramine B in HCl in the micellar phase is reported. The effect of ionic strength on the oxidation has been studied using Na₂SO₄ and the kinetics of the transition metal ion catalysed oxidation of the alcohols by Chloramine B in HCl has been studied using Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} ions.

Experimental

All the chemicals and reagents used were of AnalaR grade – geraniol and 1-phenyl ethanol (Ultra International Limited), benzyl alcohol (B.D.H.), sodium lauryl sulphate (SDS) (Loba Chemie), Chloramine T (Fluka Chemicals) and Chloramine B (Fluka Chemicals). A.R. Na₂SO₄ was used for the study of ionic strength on oxidation rate of alcohols. The metal salts required for the catalytic study were of AnalaR grade (B.D.H.).

The oxidation of the alcohols was studied between 30–50 °C under pseudounimolecular conditions with respect to the oxidising agent and its progress was monitored titrimetrically. The solutions of alcohols and oxidising agent in required amounts were allowed to equilibrate

in a previously adjusted thermostat (accuracy ±0.1 °C). Thereafter the solutions were mixed to initiate the reaction. Aliquots of the reaction mixture were withdrawn at regular time intervals and the reaction was arrested using ice. The unreacted haloamine was treated with ice cold 10% KI and dilute H₂SO₄ and the liberated iodine was titrated against standard Na₂S₂O₃ using starch as indicator.

Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} in the concentration range [M(II)] = 0.5 to 2.5 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³ were used to catalyse the oxidation of alcohols by Chloramine B in HCl. The effect of ionic strength on the oxidation rate was studied in dilute solution in the range μ = 0.1 to 0.5 mol dm⁻³ at 40 °C using Na₂SO₄.

Results and discussion

Haloamines oxidise the primary alcohols, geraniol and benzyl alcohol to the corresponding aldehydes, geraniol and benzaldehyde respectively. The secondary alcohol, 1-phenyl ethanol is oxidised to methyl phenyl ketone.

Kinetics of oxidation of alcohols by Chloramine T in NaOH in micellar phase : The rate constant of oxidation increases with alcohols concentration as expected but decreases with increase in the concentration of Chloramine T (Table 1).

In aqueous medium, Chloramine T (Ts.NCl⁻Na⁺) acts as a strong electrolyte

Ts.NCl⁻Na⁺ → Ts.NCl⁻ + Na⁺ where Ts stands for

Table 1. Rate constant data for the oxidation of alcohols by Chloramine T in NaOH

[NaOH] = 0.05 M, [SDS] = 0.05 M, Temp. = 303 K

[Alc] × 10 ¹ (mol dm ⁻³)	[CAT] × 10 ² (mol dm ⁻³)	k × 10 ⁴ (s ⁻¹)		
		Benzyl alcohol	1-Phenyl ethanol	Geraniol
1.00	0.25	3.68	4.20	3.07
1.00	0.50	3.20	3.80	2.80
1.00	1.00	2.30	2.78	2.30
1.00	1.50	1.53	1.91	1.80
1.00	2.00	1.15	1.15	1.15
1.00	2.50	1.00	0.83	0.77
0.25	0.50	0.46	0.66	1.38
0.50	0.50	0.66	0.77	1.84
0.625	0.50	0.77	0.86	2.30
0.75	0.50	0.83	0.99	2.45
0.875	0.50	1.10	1.15	2.70
1.00	0.50	1.05	1.31	3.00

Effect of ionic strength (μ) on the rate of oxidation of alcohols by Chloramine T in NaOH

[Alc] = 0.1 M, [CAT] = 0.01 M, [NaOH] = 0.025 M

[SDS] = 0.05 M, Temp. = 313 K

μ (mol dm ⁻³)	k × 10 ⁴ (s ⁻¹)		
	Benzyl alcohol	1-Phenyl ethanol	Geraniol
0.1	2.30	3.22	2.68
0.2	1.91	3.68	2.76
0.3	2.76	2.76	3.22
0.4	1.92	2.68	2.76
0.5	2.30	2.87	2.68

Activation parameters for the oxidation of alcohols by Chloramine T in NaOH

Temp. = 303 K

Substrate	E (kJ mol ⁻¹)	ΔH* (kJ mol ⁻¹)	ΔG* (kJ mol ⁻¹)	ΔS* (JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹)
Benzyl alcohol	44.67	42.16	95.03	-175.00
1-Phenyl ethanol	19.14	16.63	94.58	-258.10
Geraniol	38.29	35.78	95.03	-196.20

[CH₃-C₆H₅-SO₂). In alkaline medium, the mechanism suggested is as follows :

In the case of a secondary alcohol, the corresponding ketone is produced. The product of the reaction i.e. aldehyde/ketone was identified by 2,4-dinitro phenyl hydrozone test and confirmed by tlc.

Applying steady state statement to steps 1, 2 and 3 we get,

$$[\text{Ts.NHCl}] = \frac{K_1 [\text{Ts.NCl}^-]}{[\text{OH}^-]}$$

$$\text{and } [\text{Complex}] = \frac{k_2 [\text{Alc}] [\text{Ts.NHCl}]}{[k_{-2} + k]}$$

$$= \frac{K_1 k_2 [\text{Alc}] [\text{Ts.NCl}]}{[k_{-2} + k] [\text{OH}^-]}$$

Step 3 determines the rate of reaction hence the rate law equation is as follows :

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d [\text{Complex}]}{dt} &= k [\text{Complex}] \\ &= \frac{k K_1 k_2 [\text{Alc}] [\text{Ts.NCl}]}{[k_{-2} + k] [\text{OH}^-]} \\ &= \frac{k^1 [\text{Alc}] [\text{Ts.NCl}]}{[\text{OH}^-]} \end{aligned}$$

where $k^1 = \frac{K_1 k k_2}{[k_{-2} + k]}$

The rate law equation indicates a first order dependence on alcohol and Chloramine T and an inverse first order dependence on OH^- ions. A retarding influence of OH^- ions has been observed in the oxidation rates of several reactions involving Chloramine T in alkaline medium which is attributed to the formation of the conjugate acid, Ts.NCl^- . Thus the inverse dependence of reaction rate on $[\text{OH}^-]$ indicates that Ts.NHCl is the predominant oxidising species³.

The effect of ionic strength (μ) on the oxidation rate was studied in the range of $\mu = 0.1$ to 0.5 mol dm^{-3} using Na_2SO_4 (Table 1). Plot of $\log k$ vs $\sqrt{\mu}$ is linear.

Activation parameters were calculated from the effect of temperature on the oxidation rate in the temperature range 30°C to 50°C (Table 1). The negative values of ΔS^* suggests a reorientation of solvent molecules due to the formation of the activated complex and can be ex-

Table 2. Rate constant data for the oxidation of benzyl alcohol and 1-phenyl ethanol by Chloramine B in HCl

[HCl] = 0.1 M, [SDS] = 0.05 M, Temp. = 303 K

[Alc] × 10 ¹ (mol dm ⁻³)	[CAB] × 10 ² (mol dm ⁻³)	k × 10 ⁴ (s ⁻¹)	
		Benzyl alcohol	1-Phenyl ethanol
1.00	0.10	3.14	8.22
1.00	0.20	1.04	4.18
1.00	0.30	0.71	3.14
1.00	0.40	0.60	1.65
1.00	0.50	0.38	1.04
0.25	0.10	4.60	2.83
0.50	0.10	4.93	3.29
0.625	0.10	6.01	3.60
0.75	0.10	6.58	3.83
0.875	0.10	6.92	4.01
1.00	0.10	7.40	4.35

Effect of ionic strength on the rate of oxidation of benzyl alcohol and 1-phenyl ethanol by Chloramine B in HCl

[Alc] = 0.1 M, [CAB] = 0.001 M, [HCl] = 0.05 M, [SDS] = 0.05 M, Temp. = 313 K

μ (mol dm ⁻³)	k × 10 ⁴ (s ⁻¹)	
	Benzyl alcohol	1-Phenyl ethanol
0.1	1.43	1.14
0.2	1.53	1.19
0.3	1.79	0.99
0.4	1.53	0.97
0.5	2.30	1.15

Thermodynamic activation parameters for the oxidation of benzyl alcohol and 1-phenyl ethanol by Chloramine B in HCl

Temp. = 303 K

Substrate	E (kJ mol ⁻¹)	ΔH^* (kJ mol ⁻¹)	ΔG^* (kJ mol ⁻¹)	ΔS^* (JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹)
Benzyl alcohol	89.35	86.04	94.25	-29.00
1-Phenyl ethanol	95.75	93.22	91.83	-46.00

plained by a model in which the water molecules are tightly held to -OH bond which is the site of oxidation⁴.

The oxidation rate of alcohols by Chloramine B in HCl in micellar phase increases with alcohol concentration but decreases as the concentration of the haloamine increases (Table 2).

In aqueous medium, Chloramine B (RNCl⁻Na⁺) acts as a strong electrolyte and ionises as follows :

RNCl⁻Na⁺ → RNCl⁻ + Na⁺ where R stands for C₆H₅SO₂.

In acidic medium, the mechanism suggested is as follows :

RNHCl is the predominant oxidising species in the acidic medium.

In the case of a secondary alcohol, the corresponding ketone is formed.

Applying steady state treatment to steps 1, 2 and 3 we get,

$$[\text{RNHCl}] = K_1 [\text{RNCl}^-] [\text{H}^+]$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{and } [\text{Complex}] &= \frac{k_2 [\text{Alc}] [\text{RNHCl}]}{[k_{-2} + k]} \\ &= \frac{K_1 k_2 [\text{Alc}] [\text{RNCl}^-] [\text{H}^+]}{[k_{-2} + k]} \end{aligned}$$

Step 3 determines the rate of reaction hence the rate law equation is as follows :

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d[\text{Complex}]}{dt} &= k [\text{Complex}] \\ &= \frac{k K_1 k_2 [\text{Alc}] [\text{RNCl}^-] [\text{H}^+]}{[k_{-2} + k]} \\ &= k^1 [\text{Alc}] [\text{RNCl}^-] [\text{H}^+] \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{where } k^1 = \frac{K_1 k k_2}{[k_{-2} + k]}$$

Thus the rate law equation indicates a first order dependence on alcohol, Chloramine B and acid, The decrease of oxidation rate with [CAB] (Table 2) is due to the retardation of the protonation of RNCl⁻ at high concentration of the oxidising agent. The -SO₂ group in Chloramine B is an electron withdrawing group and makes nitrogen less basic. This greatly hinders the protonation of RNCl⁻ resulting in the observed decrease in oxidation rate with increasing [CAB]. The rate of oxidation of geraniol was found to be very high and could not be accurately measured using titrimetric method.

Na₂SO₄ in the range μ = 0.1 to 0.5 mol dm⁻³ was used to study the effect of ionic strength on oxidation rate in dilute solution which gives a linear plot. This observation is in accordance with the reaction mechanism suggested for the oxidation reaction.

Activation parameters were calculated from the effect of temperature on oxidation rate (Table 2). The negative values of ΔS^{*} indicate a decrease in the degrees of freedom due to the formation of a rigid activated complex resulting in an extensive reorientation of solvent molecules around the activated complex.

Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} were used as catalysts in the range [M(II)] = 0.5 to 2.5 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³ at 30 °C. The rate constants varied linearly with [M(II)] (Tables 3a and 3b).

Table 3a. Rate constant data for the metal ion catalysed oxidation of benzyl alcohol by Chloramine B in HCl

[Alc] = 0.1 M, [HCl] = 0.1 M, [CAB] = 0.005 M, [SDS] = 0.05 M, Temp. = 303 K

[M(II)] × 10 ³ (mol dm ⁻³)	k × 10 ⁴ (s ⁻¹)		
	Ni ^{II}	Cu ^{II}	Zn ^{II}
In absence	1.31	1.31	1.31
0.5	1.43	2.35	1.61
1.0	1.51	2.70	1.97
1.5	1.70	3.18	2.30
2.0	1.79	3.22	2.67
2.5	1.84	3.68	2.68

The reaction mechanism proposed for the metal ion catalysed oxidation of alcohols is as follows :

In aqueous medium, Chloramine B (RNCl⁻Na⁺) acts as a strong electrolyte and ionises as follows :

RNCl⁻Na⁺ → RNCl⁻ + Na⁺ where R stands for [C₆H₅SO₂]. In acidic medium,

RNHCl is the predominant oxidising species in acidic medium.

A ketone is produced in the case of a secondary alcohol.

Table 3b. Rate constant data for the metal ion catalysed oxidation of 1-phenyl ethanol by Chloramine B in HCl

[Alc] = 0.1 M, [HCl] = 0.1 M, [CAB] = 0.005 M, [SDS] = 0.05 M, Temp. = 303 K

[M(II)] × 10 ³ (mol dm ⁻³)	k × 10 ⁴ (s ⁻¹)		
	Ni ^{II}	Cu ^{II}	Zn ^{II}
In absence	7.30	7.30	7.30
0.5	11.00	23.00	36.90
1.0	14.70	25.90	46.00
1.5	18.70	29.30	55.00
2.0	21.00	54.60	64.40
2.5	26.50	65.80	76.70

The catalytic effect of transition metal ions is inversely proportional to the stability of their complexes which may be formed as short lived intermediates during the course of reaction. The stability of the complexes generally depends on the charge density of the metal ions involved in addition to many other factors. Thus the stability order for the metal ions under study is expected to be Cu^{II} > Zn^{II} > Ni^{II}⁵ and their catalytic efficiency is expected to follow the sequence Ni^{II} > Zn^{II} > Cu^{II}. However such generalisation are only very approximate guides to metal ion behaviour⁶ and discrepancies have been observed and reported in the values of stability constants of complexes and catalytic efficiency of metal ions involved⁶.

In the present investigation, discrepancies have been observed.

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